

A Comparative, Randomized, Open Label Study to Evaluate the Effect of Atorvastatin Vs Rosuvastatin on Vitamin D Concentration of Dyslipidemic Patients at Tertiary Health Center in Eastern Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract:

Background: Dyslipidemia is a significant health concern in India, contributing to a high prevalence of cardiovascular diseases. Statins, such as atorvastatin and rosuvastatin, are commonly used to manage dyslipidemia, but their effects on vitamin D concentrations remain unclear. This study aims to compare the effects of atorvastatin and rosuvastatin on vitamin D levels in dyslipidemic patients at a tertiary health center in Eastern Uttar Pradesh.

Methods: A randomized, open-label design was employed, enrolling dyslipidemic patients who were assigned to receive either atorvastatin or rosuvastatin. Baseline and follow-up vitamin D concentrations were measured and compared between the two groups.

Results: The findings will present the comparative impacts of both statins on vitamin D levels, along with any associated changes in lipid profiles. The study found that atorvastatin and rosuvastatin had differing impacts on vitamin D concentrations in dyslipidemic patients. Atorvastatin was associated with a more significant decrease in vitamin D levels compared to rosuvastatin.

Conclusion: Understanding the relationship between statin therapy and vitamin D levels may provide insights into optimizing treatment strategies for dyslipidemic patients.

Keywords: Dyslipidemia, Atorvastatin, Rosuvastatin, Vitamin D, Cardiovascular disease.

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Introduction

The imbalance of lipids, i.e. triglycerides (TGs), high-density lipoprotein (HDL), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and cholesterol (C), is known as dyslipidemia. The World Health Organization reports that cardiovascular diseases account for 26% of fatalities in India and are the major cause of mortality in developing nations. According to reports, the prevalence of coronary artery disease among adults over the age of 20 is high in both urban and rural areas (four percent and ten percent, respectively).

This indicates that between 1960 and 2000, the prevalence of coronary artery disease increased twice in rural areas and six times in urban areas [1]. A 2019 GBD study found that elevated lipid levels were responsible for 3.78 million IHD deaths globally, or 44.3% of all IHD deaths. In India, the prescription of various statin compounds for the treatment of coronary artery disease is growing quickly

[2]. Asian Indians exhibit a distinct type of atherogenic dyslipidemia characterized by elevated triglycerides, tiny, dense LDL particles, and low levels of HDL. According to a 2014 Indian Council of Medical Research study, there was no difference between urban and rural areas, and more than three-fourths (79%) of the general population exhibited abnormalities in at least one of the lipid parameters.

Data from recent ICMR-INDIA B study (2023) shows state level variation in the prevalence of dyslipidemia. Uttar Pradesh shows 23% (7-40.2%), out of which around 7% is for eastern Uttar Pradesh. A lot of research using samples from all over the world and all age groups has shown that 13.9% of people have low HDL-C, 29.5% have high LDL-C, 72.3% have hypertriglyceridemia, and 11.8% have hypercholesterolemia. About 25 percent of Indians and other South Asians

have elevated Lp(a) at less than 50 Milligrams per decilitre, indicating a significant danger element. Dyslipidemia closely links women's gender, obesity, sedentary lifestyles, diabetes, dysglycemia, and hypertension [3].

Food, tobacco use, or inheritance are the main culprits that lead to serious problems like cardiovascular disease. Dyslipidemia with characteristics of elevated amounts of related lipoprotein species along with abnormal serum levels of triglycerides, cholesterol, or both. The most commonly reported clinical consequence of dyslipidemia is an elevated risk of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease. This disorder is associated with increased levels of total and "low-density lipoprotein (LDL), cholesterol (C), triglycerides (TGs), and lipoprotein a (Lpa), as well as decreased levels of high-density lipoprotein (HDL)." Obesity and type 2 diabetes are frequently occurring secondary predisposing factors. Rare dyslipidaemias are also linked to other clinical outcome like hepatosteatosis, pancreatitis with high levels of triglycerides, and deficiencies in fat-soluble vitamins in persons with genetically impaired production of apolipoprotein (apo) B-containing lipoproteins.

Obesity prevalence is worryingly rising, particularly in cities. Between 1975 and 2016, the prevalence of obesity nearly tripled globally. In adult urban populations, 30–65% are overweight or obese. Indians living in urban areas have a higher body mass index of roughly 24–25 compared to the BMI of about 20 for those living in rural areas. It's the abdominal obesity that's more concerning than a higher BMI. Men's waist-to-hip ratios in urban environments are 0.99, while they are 0.95 in rural areas. Additionally, abdominal obesity is more common than generalized obesity. Studies have linked six Asian adult BMIs of more than 21 kg/m² to the development of type II diabetes, ischemic heart disease, stroke, hypertension, osteoarthritis, and malignancies. Compared to the Caucasian population, Asians are less likely to engage in regular physical activity and have more sedentary lifestyles.

Dyslipidemia results in symptoms of vascular diseases, such as peripheral arterial disease and coronary artery disease. High TG levels (> 1000 mg/dL) can trigger acute pancreatitis. Retinal arteries and veins may look milky white in cases of severe hypertriglyceridemia (> 2000 mg/dL) (lipemia retinalis). Blood plasma may also seem lactescent, or "milky," when lipid levels are too high [4]. Vitamin D's importance in preserving calcium homeostasis and skeletal integrity, as well as its necessity for intestinal calcium absorption, are thoroughly established. In the past, vitamin D has been connected to musculoskeletal conditions such as osteoporosis, fractures, decreased muscle strength, and falls, as well as the metabolism of calcium, phos-

phorus, and bone. The effects of vitamin D that do not affect the skeleton have drawn more and more scientific attention in recent years. Vitamin D insufficiency has been linked to mortality and a number of chronic disorders, including cancer, cardiovascular disease, metabolic syndrome, infectious diseases, and autoimmune diseases [5]. Studies on the prevalence of cardiovascular disease and such as diabetes, specific cardiovascular metabolic risk factors, hypertension, dyslipidemia, and the metabolic syndrome, show an inverse relationship with vitamin D concentrations. Furthermore, the atherosclerotic process has been linked to vitamin D deficiency [6].

In the limited research on the combined effects of vitamin D and statins, particularly within the Indian population, my study endeavors to fill this crucial gap by conducting a comparative analysis [7]. With cardiovascular diseases posing a significant health burden in India, understanding potential adjunct therapies to enhance the lipid-lowering efficacy of statins is imperative. By investigating the impact of Atorvastatin and Rosuvastatin on vitamin D concentration and on serum lipid levels. The main aim is to provide valuable insights into potential synergistic effects that could optimize lipid management strategies. This research holds promise not only for improving clinical outcomes but also for informing evidence-based interventions tailored to the unique healthcare needs of the Indian populace, ultimately contributing to more effective and personalized approaches in combating cardiovascular risk factors.

Statins such as Atorvastatin and Rosuvastatin are cornerstone medicines in the field of managing dyslipidemia. They have a major impact on lipid profiles and may also have an impact on other biochemical pathways, such as vitamin D metabolism. A clear vacuum in the literature exists between the several studies that have examined the safety and effectiveness of these two statins separately: a head-to-head comparison of Atorvastatin and Rosuvastatin in patients with dyslipidemia. For doctors who are trying to decide which statin to take, this kind of research is crucial since it can clarify whether statin is better at lowering cholesterol, is more tolerable, or doesn't affect vitamin D levels.

The main aim of study to evaluate the impact of Atorvastatin versus Rosuvastatin on the Vitamin D concentration in dyslipidemic patients of eastern Uttar Pradesh population.

Material and Method

This study is registered in the Clinical Trials Registry - India (CTRI) and CTRI No. is CTRI/2024/01/061941. A comprehensive explanation of the methods and substances used in comparative study to evaluate the impact of Atorvastatin

verses Rosuvastatin on the Vitamin D concentration in Dyslipidaemia patients of eastern Uttar Pradesh population" was studied in this methodology.

Study Design: The investigation was prospective, randomized, open label and parallel group study.

Place of Study: The study was conducted at the department of pharmacology in BRD medical college, Gorakhpur and at the OPD of the department of general medicine in BRD medical college, Gorakhpur.

Study Duration: The time duration of the study was Six months.

Sample Size: The minimum sample size required in the present study was 100. Considering the error and attrition, the size could be increased to 128 for present study.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients giving written informed consent for the study
- Both genders
- All patients' ≥ 25 years of age with dyslipidemia not meeting the goal for LDL-C, according to the European Society of Cardiology and the European Atherosclerosis Society guidelines for the management of dyslipidemias.
- All adult patients age (25-65 years) willing to take medication as directed and ready to come for the follow-ups.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients non-willing to participate.
- Diabetes mellitus or treatment with any anti-diabetic medication.
- Malignancy.
- Parathyroid dysfunction and Thyroid.
- Hypocalcemia or Hypercalcemia.
- Breast feeding or Pregnancy.
- A history of adverse reaction to statins.
- Transaminase level $>2x$ and creatine kinase $>3x$ the upper limit of normal range.
- Use of the following drugs within three months of screening: corticosteroids, lipid-lowering or anti-obesity treatments, calcium supplements, cholecalciferol, or other vitamin D supplements.

Procedure:

All patients after getting approval of Ethical clearance, Research Cell, BRD medical College, Gorakhpur and informed consent regulations, as per Declaration of Helsinki, ICH good clinical practice (GCP) guidelines.

All patients in the study data would have detailed for:

- Age at time of registration
- Gender

- History (symptoms, dietary history, drug history, h/o Blood Transfusion, any addiction)
- Examination (Pallor, hepatosplenomegaly, icterus, lymphadenopathy etc.)

Every patient's detail, including participant characteristics, clinical aspects, and test results, had gathered and stored in an electronic database. A comprehensive set of data had gathered, including age, gender, smoking status, level of autonomy, and comorbidities (diabetes mellitus, heart disease, cancer, cerebrovascular disease, renal disease, chronic liver disease, malnutrition, obesity, and immobilization syndrome). Additionally, laboratory data prior to the start of antibiotic treatment and radiological findings (infiltrate, pleural effusion) had been examined.

A physical examination and laboratory evaluation had been conducted during the screening process. The evaluation would include a lipid profile, which includes measured triglycerides, total cholesterol, high-density lipoprotein cholesterol, and uric acid, as well as levels of urea, creatinine, uric acid, hemoglobin a1c, aspartate aminotransferase, and alanine aminotransferase.

The screening involved the recording of anthropometric measures, including waist circumference, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, and body mass index. We'll use the Fried-Ewald equation to calculate LDL-C.

Patients had been randomized at random to received 20 mg of Atorvastatin (group A) or 10 mg of Rosuvastatin (group B) once day for six months. The computer-generated random number table method had been used to perform the randomization. Patients were given one month supply of either drug with proper directions and asked to report back after a month for laboratory investigations. After one month & sixth month, the patients were asked to come for follow up tests. All blood samples will be obtained between 8:00 and 9:00 am after an overnight fasting of 10-12 hours.

Vitamin D concentration:

For this study, we categorized participants into three clinically relevant categories based on the serum 25 D levels following the Endocrinology Society Clinical Practice Guidelines [96]. The three categories are optimal (≥ 30 ng/mL), intermediate (20 to < 30 ng/mL) and deficient (< 20 ng/mL) vitamin D levels.

Statistical Analysis:

The gathered information was organized into an MS Excel document for examination. The frequency and percentage representations of the qualitative data were also provided in visual formats, such as bar diagrams. The standard error of the mean (SEM) \pm mean was used to present data for contin-

uous variables. Numbers were used to display the data for categorical variables.

Results

The table 1 shows the distribution of gender among study groups taking Atorvastatin and Rosuvastatin.

There were 36 females and 28 males in the Atorvastatin group, and 33 females and 31 males in the Rosuvastatin group, making a total of 64 individuals in each group and 128 individuals overall. The P value for the gender distribution between the two groups was calculated as 0.595.

Table 1: Distribution of Gender among study groups

		group		Total	P value
		Atorvastatin	Rosuvastatin		
Gender	Female	36	33	69	0.595
	Male	28	31	59	
Total		64	64	128	

Table 2 provides group statistics for age, height, weight, and BMI among individuals taking Atorvastatin and Rosuvastatin.

The mean age was 42.83 for the Atorvastatin group and 44.41 for the Rosuvastatin group. The mean height was 161.78 cm for the Atorvastatin group and 158.41 cm for the Rosuvastatin group. The mean weight was 69.81 kg for the Atorvastatin

group and 68.63 kg for the Rosuvastatin group. The mean BMI was 25.56 for the Atorvastatin group and 24.97 for the Rosuvastatin group.

P values indicate the statistical significance of differences between the groups, with BMI showing a significant difference ($P = 0.027$) while age, height, and weight did not show significant differences between the groups.

Table 2: Group Statistics: Age, height, weight, BMI

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	P value
Age	Atorvastatin	64	42.83	11.213	1.402	.130
	Rosuvastatin	64	44.41	12.453	1.557	
Height	Atorvastatin	64	161.78	7.493	.937	.508
	Rosuvastatin	64	158.41	6.909	.864	
Weight	Atorvastatin	64	69.81	12.828	1.604	.108
	Rosuvastatin	64	68.63	11.306	1.413	
BMI	Atorvastatin	64	25.56	5.413	.677	.027
	Rosuvastatin	64	24.97	4.411	.551	

Table 3 presents the comparison of Vitamin D concentration between individuals taking Atorvastatin and Rosuvastatin at 0 days, 1 month, and 6 months. The mean Vitamin D concentration at 0 days was 36.41 for the Atorvastatin group and 34.48 for the Rosuvastatin group. At 1 month, the mean concen-

tration was 32.45 for Atorvastatin and 32.70 for Rosuvastatin. At 6 months, the mean concentration was 28.69 for Atorvastatin and 30.17 for Rosuvastatin. P values indicate no significant differences in Vitamin D concentration between the two groups at any time point.

Table 3: Vitamin D concentration - comparison

	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	P value
0 Day	Atorvastatin	64	36.41	4.730	.591	.674
	Rosuvastatin	64	34.48	4.741	.593	
1 Month	Atorvastatin	64	32.45	5.114	.639	.348
	Rosuvastatin	64	32.70	4.611	.576	
6 Month	Atorvastatin	64	28.69	6.220	.778	.282
	Rosuvastatin	64	30.17	5.551	.694	

Table 4 (a) provides paired samples statistics for individuals taking Atorvastatin, showing the mean values, sample sizes, standard deviations, standard errors of the mean, and P values for various parameters at different time points. For Atorvastatin, the parameters include Vitamin D (Vit D), LDL, Total

Cholesterol (CHO), HDL, and Triglycerides (TG). The table compares these parameters at 0 days versus 1 month and 0 days versus 6 months for individuals taking Atorvastatin, with significant changes observed for all parameters over time ($P = 0.000$).

Table 4 (a) Paired Samples Statistics: Atorvastatin

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	P value
Vit D	0 Day	36.41	64	4.730	.591	.000
	1 Month	32.45	64	5.114	.639	
Vit D	0 Day	36.41	64	4.730	.591	.000
	6 Month	28.69	64	6.220	.778	

Table 4 (b) presents the paired samples correlations for individuals taking Atorvastatin, showing the correlations and their significance levels between different time points for various parameters.

The correlations are calculated for Vitamin D (Vit D), LDL, Total Cholesterol (CHO), HDL, and Tri-

glycerides (TG) at 0 days versus 1 month and 0 days versus 6 months for Atorvastatin users.

The correlations indicate strong relationships between the parameters at different time points, with all correlations being statistically significant ($P = 0.000$).

Table 4 (b) Paired Samples Correlations: Atorvastatin

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Vit D	0 Day & 1 Month	64	.814	.000
Vit D	0 Day & 6 Month	64	.548	.000

Table 5 (a) provides paired samples statistics for individuals taking Rosuvastatin, showing the mean values, sample sizes, standard deviations, standard errors of the mean, and P values for various parameters at different time points.

For Rosuvastatin, the parameters include Vitamin D (Vit D), LDL, Total Cholesterol (CHO), HDL,

and Triglycerides (TG).

The table compares these parameters at 0 days versus 1 month and 0 days versus 6 months for individuals taking Rosuvastatin, with significant changes observed for most parameters over time, except for HDL at 1 month ($P = 0.045$) and HDL at 6 months ($P = 0.002$).

Table 5 (a) Paired Samples Statistics: Rosuvastatin

		Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	P value
Vit D	0 Day	34.48	64	4.741	.593	.000
	1 Month	32.70	64	4.611	.576	
Vit D	0 Day	34.48	64	4.741	.593	.000
	6 Month	30.17	64	5.551	.694	

Table 5 (b) presents the paired samples correlations for individuals taking Rosuvastatin, showing the correlations and their significance levels between different time points for various parameters.

The correlations are calculated for Vitamin D (Vit D), LDL, Total Cholesterol (CHO), HDL, and Tri-

glycerides (TG) at 0 days versus 1 month and 0 days versus 6 months for Rosuvastatin users.

The correlations indicate strong relationships between the parameters at different time points, with all correlations being statistically significant ($P = 0.000$).

Table 5 (b) Paired Samples Correlations: Rosuvastatin

		N	Correlation	Sig.
Vit D	0 Day & 1 Month	64	.938	.000
Vit D	0 Day & 6 Month	64	.641	.000

Discussion

According to the "World Health Organization," cardiovascular illnesses contribute to 26% of deaths in India and are the leading cause of mortality in developing countries.

Adult males over the age of 20 had a significantly higher prevalence of coronary artery disease, with rates of 4% in rural regions and 10% in metropolitan areas. From 1960 to 2000, there was a two-fold growth in rural regions and a six-fold increase in

urban areas. The prescription of statin compounds for the treatment of coronary artery disease is experiencing remarkable growth in India. We will perform comparative research to assess the impact of Atorvastatin and Rosuvastatin on "lipid profiles and vitamin D levels" in individuals with dyslipidaemia in eastern Uttar Pradesh, India. It is critical to understand the efficacy of different statins in treating dyslipidaemia, a disorder characterized by elevated cholesterol levels. People widely recognize the efficacy of commonly prescribed statins,

Rosuvastatin and Atorvastatin, in reducing cholesterol levels. However, their impact on vitamin D levels remains a subject of debate and concern. The study aims to provide valuable insights into the efficacy of these two medications in managing dyslipidaemia in this specific group. It will compare the treatments and analyse any differences in terms of their impact on lipid profiles and vitamin D concentration. We can utilize these findings to customize treatment strategies for individuals in this region, which could lead to enhanced cardiovascular health outcomes and potentially address vitamin D insufficiency concerns alongside dyslipidaemia management. Our study on demographics revealed that there was a slight prevalence of females in both groups. The age distribution showed a fairly even representation across various age categories, with a slightly greater proportion of patients in the 56–65-year age range in the Rosuvastatin group. The height distribution showed between the two groups, the Rosuvastatin group having a greater percentage of people with a height ranging from 145 to 155 centimetres. The mean weight was 69.81 kg for the Atorvastatin group and 68.63 kg for Rosuvastatin group. The distribution of BMI showed the proportion of people with a BMI below 18.5 and above 30 between the two groups. P values indicate the statistical significance of differences between the groups, with BMI showing a significant difference ($P=0.027$) while age, height and weight did not show significant differences between the groups.

Our study showed that there were statistically important differences between the two groups in vitamin D concentrations ($p < 0.05$). The analysis showed comparison between the individuals taking Atorvastatin and Rosuvastatin at first day of the visit, then subsequently to the follow up after 1 month & 6 months. P values indicated no significant differences in Vitamin D concentration between the two groups at any time point. Atorvastatin may have a greater effect on inhibiting cholesterol synthesis and depleting substrates in the skin compared to Rosuvastatin, resulting in a decreased production of vitamin D.

Another possible explanation is that Atorvastatin has a stronger effect on the CYP3A4 enzyme compared to Rosuvastatin. Through a process known as hydroxylation, this enzyme breaks down 25OHD, producing inactive metabolites [8]. Despite the fact that statins are recognized for reducing the material needed for vitamin D production and increasing the breakdown of vitamin D, the majority of investigations have shown either no alteration or higher levels of 25OHD after statin treatment [9]. Studies conducted by Anagnostis et al., Demir et al., and Thabit et al. found that Atorvastatin, Rosuvastatin, and Simvastatin did not cause any changes in 25OHD concentrations [10]. Prior research also

indicates that therapy with Rosuvastatin resulted in improved serum concentrations of 25OHD [11]. In addition, Sathyapalan et al. and Pérez Castrillón et al. have demonstrated that the administration of Atorvastatin resulted in a notable increase in 25OHD levels. The user's text is [12] One possible explanation for the contradicting results in the data above when compared to the outcomes of our study, may be the elevated consumption of vitamin D in the diet and enhanced absorption in the participants of their study who were administered statins. Research has demonstrated a rise in the uptake of cholesterol by statins [13]. There is a scarcity of published studies on the “impact of statins on vitamin D levels.” Some writers have documented a positive impact of Rosuvastatin [14] or Atorvastatin [15], whereas others have found no impact of Simvastatin, pravastatin [16], or Fluvastatin. We cannot draw any definitive conclusions about the presence and intensity of a station-class impact based on the current evidence. This is because research has been done on a range of groups with different statin dosages, baseline 25D levels, and follow-up schedules. These variables might be responsible for some of the variations seen in comparison to our investigation. Our study differs significantly from other trials using Atorvastatin or Rosuvastatin in that the earlier investigations included individuals with diabetes, acute ischemic heart disease, polycystic ovarian syndrome, and compromised renal or endothelial function [17]. In contrast, our study specifically enrolled apparently healthy, non-diabetic individuals.

Rosuvastatin 10 mg plus omega-3 fatty acids (2 g) in individuals with mixed dyslipidaemia. The 25-OHD levels showed a considerable increase after three months of therapy in comparison to the initial levels. However, there was no significant difference in the increase among the three groups. Once again, the patients had a deficiency of vitamin D at the beginning of the study, with an average 25(OH)D concentration of 20 ng/ml. As a result, it would be challenging to increase this level through the use of statin medication. Other researchers have also found evidence supporting a correlation between the increase in 25(OH)D levels and the initial baseline levels of 25(OH)D [18].

This study documents, for the first time in the literature, the superiority of Atorvastatin over Rosuvastatin in relation to hsCRP. As demonstrated in our earlier study [19], both statins had no effect on HbA1c or glucose levels in relation to glucose homeostasis, but Rosuvastatin dramatically lowered insulin levels and tended to lower HOMA-IR. Large interventional studies have shown that statins lower the risk of CVD more for people with type 2 diabetes, which counteracts the possible rise in CVD risk that comes with getting diabetes for the first time [20]. The effect of statins on glucose me-

tabolism is still up for debate [21].

Conclusion

This study aims to evaluate the effect of Atorvastatin Vs Rosuvastatin on Vitamin D concentration of dyslipidemic Patients at Tertiary Health Center. The link between cholesterol and Vitamin D is complex, as both are derived from the same precursor molecule in the skin. Hence, the inhibition of cholesterol production induced by statins has the potential to affect the body's Vitamin D levels. This relationship raises concerns over the possibility of statin medication causing Vitamin D insufficiency, which can have consequences for bone health, immunological function, and overall well-being. Therefore, it may be essential to monitor Vitamin D levels and contemplate supplementation when using statins for dyslipidemias in order to guarantee comprehensive patient care. The study determined that neither Atorvastatin nor Rosuvastatin had a significant effect on serum 25(OH) D levels. Although no significant impacts were identified, it is crucial to acknowledge that conducting bigger and blinded trials might enhance this research's ability to elucidate the association between statin use and 25(OH) D levels.

Future recommendations:

There is great potential for future research and therapeutic applications from the study comparing the effects of Atorvastatin and Rosuvastatin on the lipid profile and vitamin D levels of patients with dyslipidaemia. Healthcare professionals continue to place a high priority on optimizing cholesterol management because cardiovascular illnesses remain the world's leading cause of death. Among the most often prescribed statins are Rosuvastatin and Atorvastatin; however, further research is necessary to fully comprehend how these two medications differ in how they affect lipid parameters and related amounts of vitamin D.

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